

Methylammonium Rotational dynamics in Lead Halide Perovskite by Classical Molecular Dynamics: The Role of Temperature

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Abstract

An interatomic model potential for molecular dynamics is derived from first-principles and used to study the molecular rotations and relaxation times in methylammonium lead halide, here considered the prototypical example of a hybrid crystal with a strong reorientational dynamics. Within the limits of a simple ionic scheme, the potential is able to catch the main qualitative features of the material at zero and finite temperature and opens the way to the development of classical potentials for hybrid perovskites. In agreement with experiments and previous theoretical findings the molecule trajectories exhibit a transition from a dynamics dominated by high symmetry directions at low temperature, to a fast dynamics at room temperature in which the molecule can reorient quasi-randomly. By computing the angular time correlation function we discuss the reorientational time as a function of temperature in comparison with existing literature providing a simple model and a clear attribution of the relaxation times in terms of their temperature dependence. This work clarifies the temperature dependence of the relaxation times and the interpretation of the experimental data in terms of the different mechanisms contributing to the molecules dynamics.

Graphical TOC Entry

Keywords: Hybrid perovskites; Relaxation Times; Correlation Functions; Interatomic potential for hybrid materials;

Molecular rotations play an important role in the dynamical and relaxation properties of a wide class of molecular systems including organic and hybrid materials. Rotational disorder can be found in gas and liquids as well as in hard matter (e.g. hybrid perovskites).¹ A wide variety of experimental techniques including dielectric relaxation, infrared and Raman spectroscopy, spin relaxation, and fluorescence depolarization have all been employed to provide information about the relaxation times, necessary to restore the equilibrium upon a suitable perturbation of the molecular motion (typically an electromagnetic field).²

The statistical description of such phenomena is almost universally based on the use of a diffusion equation that is a suitable theoretical basis when the molecular reorientation takes place through small angular steps (e.g. large molecules in liquids).¹ Generalized models have been proposed for rotational diffusion in gas phases with angular diffusion steps of arbitrary size allowed.¹ Also models for molten salts and rotation in solids have been developed.²⁻⁴ In all cases the relaxation process is described by exponentially decaying functions including oscillating terms and containing parameters such as times between collisions, reorientational angles, inelastic contributions, rotator frequencies² that can be estimated *a posteriori* on the experimental data. Exact solutions are possible only for the simplest cases and the attribution of the model parameters is not always unique so that the models retain often a phenomenological character.² This is particularly critical for the intermediate physical regime between free diffusive and phononic-like dynamics expected for example in hybrid organic-inorganic materials.⁵

Atomistic methods can be used to complement the statistical approach in anisotropic models and other complex systems.⁶ By including explicitly the interatomic forces and by solving the atomic trajectories over suitably long time scales this approach can be effective to understand molecular rotations in structurally and chemically complex environments.⁷

In the present work a novel atomistic potential derived from first-principles is used to

study the nature of molecular rotations and relaxation times in methylammonium lead halide perovskite, here considered the prototypical example of a hybrid crystal with a strong reorientational dynamics.

Many of the properties of hybrid perovskites have been extensively studied: crystallographic structure,⁸ phase transformations,^{9,10} dielectric properties¹¹ and cation ordering.⁵ Recently, hybrid lead halides have emerged as the record material for low cost photovoltaics¹²⁻¹⁸. Hybrid perovskites can be in fact processed from solution at low temperature, forming crystalline films that are cheap but still having excellent absorption and transport properties, suitable for photovoltaics,¹⁶ optoelectronics,¹⁵ lasing¹⁹ and photocatalysis²⁰. These exceptional combination originates from the complementary role of its organic and inorganic components.²¹⁻²³

Though the localized molecular levels do not participate directly to the optical processes, the role of the molecules and its rotations on the electronic properties are nevertheless important. Rotations can affect locally the Pb-I lattice and the octahedra rotations and, in turn, the electronic gap and the effective mass tensor as already shown by first-principles calculations.²¹ A comprehensive understanding of the rotations in perovskites and the interplay between organic cation and inorganic lattice¹⁰ is of great fundamental relevance for the material properties. The dynamical orientational disorder is expected to contribute to the entropy and thermodynamics, to thermal transport, cooling of excitations, material stability, phase transitions, polarizability, infrared absorption. Furthermore, there are a number of technological issues related to the stability of the material that could depend on the reordering of the molecules within the material. In particular there is a great interest on the possible spontaneous polarization of the hybrid perovskites²⁴⁻²⁶ with the formation of ordered molecular domains. It has been proposed that the formation of such domains could have some impact on the photovoltaic properties. The stability of the molecular ordering against temperature and the ability of the molecules to change their directions (relaxation dynamics) is a fundamental aspect of this problem that requires a deep understanding of the

molecular trajectories at finite temperatures.

A fast picosecond relaxation process of the molecules in the hybrid perovskites was demonstrated experimentally by dielectric measurements and it was attributed to a dynamic disorder of the methylammonium group in the high-temperature phases.⁸ Molecular rotations at room temperature were also suggested by nuclear magnetic resonance in deuterated perovskites⁵ interpreted with an extremely rapid overall reorientation (in the picosecond or subpicosecond scale) of the N-C axis of the molecule.⁵ The role of molecules arrangements in the material have been investigated also theoretically by first-principle methods.²³ Ordered molecular and ferroelectric phases have been suggested at low temperature on the basis of static total-energy calculations.^{24,25} At room temperature instead, recent ab initio molecular dynamics simulations^{25,27,28} show a fast rotation of molecules. However, due to their numerical complexity, ab initio methods can afford simulations of limited size (typically < 100 atoms) and time scales.

Here, we follow an alternative approach in which first principles calculations are used to derive a classical model potential for hybrid perovskites (hereafter named MYP) that reproduces at a much lower computational cost (scaling linearly with the number of atoms) the main properties of the material. The MYP model is applied to study the reorientational dynamics of molecules (angular trajectories and time correlation functions of individual molecules) at finite temperatures. Time correlation functions are calculated and explained by a simple analytical model providing a clear interpretation of the relaxation times in terms of their temperature dependence.

1 The interatomic MYP model potential for hybrid perovskites

The classical MYP interatomic model is the sum of organic-organic U_{OO} , organic-inorganic U_{OI} and inorganic-inorganic U_{II} interactions and it is fitted on a dataset obtained by first

principle calculations on methylammonium lead iodide, MPbI₃, where M refers to the methylammonium ion CH₃NH₃. The U_{OO} term contains the intramolecular and intermolecular interactions of the organic cations and it is described by the standard AMBER force field including bonds, angles, dihedrals, electrostatic and dispersive interactions.²⁹ The U_{II} inorganic interactions between Pb-I are described by Buckingham potential similarly to models developed for inorganic perovskites by Matsui and coworkers.³⁰ In the spirit of previous works,^{31,32} the hybrid interactions are described as the sum of Buckingham (Buck), electrostatic, and Lennard-Jones 12-6 (LJ) terms:

$$U_{IO} = \sum_{ij} \left[A_{ij} e^{-r_{ij}/\rho_{ij}} - \frac{\sigma_{ij}}{r_{ij}^6} \right] + \sum_{ij} \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{Z_i Z_j}{r_{ij}} + \sum_{ij} \epsilon_{ij} \left[\left(\frac{s_{ij}}{r_{ij}^{12}} \right) - \left(\frac{s_{ij}}{r_{ij}^6} \right)^6 \right]$$

The fitting procedure consisted in several steps: (i) we started from a model for CsPbI₃ obtained by a suitable rescaling of the parameters of an existing parametrization for MgSiO₃;³⁰ (ii) the standard GAFF²⁹ parametrization was used for CH₃NH₃+ organic molecule with the point charges fitted against the electrostatic DFT potential of the isolated cation in +1 charge state (calculated by the TURBOMOLE code³³ with a def-TZVP basis set and BP86 exchange-correlation functional); (iii) the hybrid interactions (Pb,I)-(C,H,N) were obtained as the sum of the electrostatic potential between the the atomic partial charges of the isolated components plus Buckingham terms for the (Pb,I)-(C,N) interactions and LJ terms for H-Pb and H-N interactions. The use of the Buckingham terms to describe the hybrid (Pb,I)-(C,N) interactions (instead of LJs) was made for similarity with the case of inorganic perovskites and provided better numerical stability during finite temperature simulations. The C-Pb,N-Pb and C-I,N-I parameters were initially set equal to the inorganic interactions Cs-Pb and Cs-I, respectively. The C-I Buckingham repulsive term was set equal to N-I for simple consistency and to reduce the number of free parameters. This model was then refined by fitting all the parameters (the methylammonium atomic partial charges, the LJ and the Buckingham potential parameters for (I,Pb)-(Pb,I)) in order to model: (i) the DFT cohesive

energy curve of a perovskite cubic crystal under hydrostatic deformations (including bulk modulus, cohesive energy, lattice parameters of the material); (ii) the DFT energy curve corresponding to a collective reorientation of the molecules with respect to the inorganic lattice; (iii) the DFT energy cost associated to Pb-I distortions in order to reproduce the spontaneous octahedra rotations at low temperature and the orthorhombic ground-state structure. Further refinements were then performed to calibrate transition temperatures and the stability of the free (001) crystalline surfaces at finite temperatures. Particularly important is the calibration of the N-I interaction to reproduce the orthorhombic-to-tetragonal transition temperature (see Supporting Information). The potential parameters are reported in the Supporting Information. The goal of the fitting procedure was the formulation of a simple yet accurate model that reproduces the main qualitative features of the material at zero and finite temperatures. Further refinements of the model are in principle possible by the calibration of a set of parameters which in the current version are set to zero. However, it is likely that more complex functionals of the atomic coordinates will be necessary to improve the description of the covalent character of the material beyond the present ionic model.

In the next paragraph it is discussed the model accuracy with respect to ab initio data concerning the interaction between the molecule and the inorganic scaffold and the phase transitions that are the most relevant properties for the present investigation.

Zero temperature analysis of the hybrid interactions

The free parameters of the model potential were adjusted so as to reproduce two important properties: (i) the total energy of the bulk perovskite under hydrostatic deformation and (ii) the energy profile during the reorientation of the molecule with respect to the inorganic lattice. Results for the cohesive energy as a function of lattice spacing are reported in left panel of Figure 1 together with experimental values and DFT. All the classical calculations were performed by the DLPOLY code;³⁴ DFT calculations were performed by the plane-wave Quantum ESPRESSO code³⁵ with PBE exchange correlation functional, ultrasoft-

pseudo potentials for all atomic species, 35 Rydberg kinetic energy cutoff, 250 Rydberg charge density cutoff, 6x6x6 Monkhorst-Pack reciprocal space sampling. Since GGA tends to overestimate the lattice parameter and for a better comparison of the data, the DFT curve has been shifted with its minimum at the MYP value (see Supporting Information). The MYP data falls nicely within the experimental range (dashed region). In addition MYP gives bulk modulus (0.18 Mbar) and the cohesive energy (7.5 eV / stoichiometric unit) in reasonable agreement with DFT GGA. Concerning the rotational energy, the result is reported in Figure 1 showing a very good agreement between DFT and MYP for the rotation of the molecules within one of (001) equivalent high symmetry plane (the cubic periodicity is imposed during the rotation). The calculated energy rotational barrier turns out to be comparable to the atomic thermal energy at room temperature (see Figure 1). The static barrier calculated for the collective rotation is an upper limit of the real activation energy that is lower because of atomic relaxations, entropic contributions and more favorable rotational paths. These effects will be naturally included in molecular dynamics simulations at finite temperature and the results will be discussed below.

Figure 1: (Left panel): Energy as a function of lattice spacing of the cubic $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{PbI}_3$ bulk during a hydrostatic deformation for the MYP model potential and for *ab initio* DFT-GGA (shifted to the MYP minimum). Atomistic data are fit by the universal energy relation.³⁶ (Right Panel) Total-energy of the cubic $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{PbI}_3$ bulk (cubic periodicity imposed) during a rotation of the molecular cation (by starting from the DFT minimum energy configuration for the cubic phase) within a (001) crystallographic plane (see top insets); black and red curves are DFT and MP respectively (Top panels: snapshots showing the molecule during the rotation). The rotational barrier is ~ 45 meV/atom corresponding to 0.54 eV/cation or 52 kJ/mol.

Finite temperature analysis of the hybrid perovskite bulk

In this Section we show that the main structural and thermodynamical features of the material are reproduced. To this aim we start from the DFT lowest energy orthorhombic unit cell (P0 crystal structure according to Ref. 22), replicated four times along each crystallographic direction, so forming a crystal of 3024 atoms. We performed a series of constant temperature constant stress $N\sigma T$ simulations under zero stress during which the metric tensor was allowed to fluctuate without symmetry constraints. Each system was equilibrated for at least 0.3 ns at constant temperature in the range 0-400 K.

Figure 2: (Top panel) Snapshots of the $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{PbI}_3$ crystal at 100 K (left) and 300 K (right) during zero stress $N\sigma T$ run; octahedra formed by Pb and I atoms are represented in gold; C,N,H atoms are light-blue, dark-blue and white, respectively. Pseudo-cubic lattice (i.e. $V^{1/3}$) (middle panel) and anisotropy factor (bottom panel) of MPbI_3 as a function of temperature calculated by MYP (circles) compared to experiments (small circles,¹⁷ triangles⁸).

Snapshots of the systems (obtained by using the VMD package³⁷) at 100 K (Figure 2 left) and 300 K (right) clearly show the stability of the crystalline structure. In particular the snapshot at 100 K shows the $a^-a^-c^+$ tilting pattern³⁸ proper of the orthorhombic Pnma structure, while at room temperature the $a^0a^0c^-$ tilting pattern of the tetragonal phase is clearly visible. Figure 2, middle and bottom panels, report the volume per formula unit and the anisotropy ratio, respectively, as function of temperature and compared with two set of experimental data.^{8,17} Experiments show that methylammonium lead halide perovskite has an orthorhombic crystalline structure at low temperature, below 160 K with three different lattice parameters. The corresponding anisotropy (i.e the ratio between the largest and the

minimum parameters, indicated by c/b) is sizable at low temperatures (100-150 K). As the temperature increases the distortions of the Pb-I octahedra induce a higher degree of symmetry resulting in a jump at ~ 160 K followed by a continuous decrease of the anisotropy down to $c/b \sim 1$ when the cubic phase is reached (above room 300 K). As for the density, experiments show that it increases with temperature with discontinuities and large fluctuations at the phase transition around 160-200 K.

The MYP calculations compare well with experiments: (i) at low temperature it is found an orthorhombic crystal with a sizable anisotropy and a discontinuity in the same temperature range 160-180 K; (ii) the anisotropy is found to decrease with temperature until the formation of cubic phase above room temperature (iii) the phase transition orthorhombic-to-tetragonal reported experimentally at 160 K has a counterpart in the change of slope observable in the volume evolution with temperature (though smaller than experiments); (iv) the volume increases with temperature and it is within the experimental data in the high temperature phase 160-350 K where the rotations are important. Discrepancies with respect to experiments are possible for such a simple ionic model (not including charge redistribution and covalent bonding). Further improvements will probably require the use of environment-dependent many-body terms able to better describe the covalent character of the Pb-I interactions and the anisotropy in the octahedra.

However, the overall good agreement reported above, between MYP and the main relevant properties of the material, is a robust basis for the study of molecular rotations.

Finite temperature dynamics of methylammonium in hybrid perovskites

Figure 3: (Left panel) Cross section view of the orthorhombic crystal at $T=100$ K representing a single molecular a-b plane; the checkboard molecular pattern can be recognized, that is in agreement with DFT findings;²² the direction of each molecule (red arrow corresponding to the N-C axis) with respect to the inorganic lattice is defined by the rotation within the a-b plane (azimuthal angle ϕ , middle panel) and by the tilt with respect to the c direction (the polar angle θ , right panel).

The ability of the molecules to rotate can be analyzed by several methods. We consider first the equilibrium distribution of molecular directions. The direction \hat{n} is specified by its N-C backbone (see Figure 3). We adopt a spherical coordinate system with the polar axis along the c crystallographic direction and θ and ϕ polar and azimuthal angles, respectively (see middle and right panels in Figure 3); the instantaneous molecule orientation $\hat{n}=(\sin\theta\cos\phi, \sin\theta\sin\phi, \cos\theta)$ can be described by a point in the $(\phi, z = \cos\theta)$ plane. The use of $z = \cos\theta$ is preferable to θ since a distribution of orientations with equal probability gives a uniform map in (ϕ, z) plane, being the element of area $dS(\phi, \theta) = d(\cos\theta)d\phi = dzd\phi$. In Figure 4 the distribution of orientations is reported as a function of temperature. At 100 K the molecules vibrate around preferential high symmetry crystallographic orientations giving rise to a map with two spots centered at $\phi = 0, 180^\circ$ and $z \sim 0$. Each spot consists of two lobes due to the molecules that are not parallel to the a direction and tend to be facial with respect to the Pbl cage (see Figure 3, middle panel). The directional map is periodic with

period 180° along ϕ and this corresponds to molecules oriented in opposite directions. In fact, it is found that the molecules of neighboring a - c planes (along the c direction) tend to be antiparallel.

Figure 4: Directional maps ($\phi, z = \cos\theta$) as a function of temperature. The maps are obtained by considering the directions of all the 256 molecules of the crystal, sampled every 30 fs during 10 ps of annealing at constant temperature $N\sigma T$

At 150 K the molecules are still aligned around $z=0$ (i.e. $\theta = 90^\circ$) but an increasing density of points is found out of the main spots ($z = \cos\theta \neq 0$), revealing the ability of the molecules to deviate in response to thermal fluctuations. In the range 150-180 K the system undergoes the phase transition from the orthorhombic to the tetragonal phase and the maps display sizable collective fluctuations. In particular at 160 K the average orientations of the molecules change towards $z=+1, -1$ (i.e. polar angles $\theta \sim 0^\circ$ and $\theta \sim 180^\circ$). This

indicate that during the phase transition the molecules can undergo a collective reorientation switching from the a - b plane into a more vertical orientation along the azimuthal directions -45° and 135° . Similar features are found at 155 K and 165 K (see Supporting Information) At 170 K the molecules recover an average planar orientation at $z=0$ (i.e. $\theta \sim 90^\circ$) but the map exhibits a new feature consisting of two ellipses that emerge from the two main spots. This corresponds to a rotational regime in which the molecules are able to rotate though most of the density is still along the high symmetry directions. Hereupon, the molecules are able to explore a much larger configurational space and the distribution becomes more uniform. The maps consist now of stripes centered at azimuthal angles $\phi = -45^\circ, 45^\circ, 135^\circ, 225^\circ$ (i.e. facial with respect to the PBI lattice) while polar angles are explored almost uniformly from planar to vertical molecular orientations. As the temperature increases the points accumulate also at $z = -1, +1$ indicating a larger number of molecules that align along the z direction and the distribution tends to be more and more uniform.

Figure 5: Time evolution of the molecular direction $\cos\theta(t)$ (with respect to its initial direction) calculated for two randomly selected molecules (continuous and dashed lines) at $T=170$ K (top panel) and $T=300$ K (bottom panel) .

The above analysis provides evidence of an important temperature effect. In order to characterize the kinetics we calculate the cosine trajectory $\cos\theta_i(t-t_0)$, i.e. the angle spanned by the molecular direction as a function of time t :

$$\cos\theta_i(t-t_0) = \hat{n}_i(t) \cdot \hat{n}_i(t_0)$$

where $\hat{n}_i(t_0)$ is the orientation of the molecule at the initial time t_0 . Examples of trajectories (only two molecules are shown for clarity) are reported in Figure 5. By definitions the trajectories start from the point $(0, 1)$. At $T=170$ K (top panel) the molecules remain in the upper half of the diagram where $\cos\theta > 0$ and $\theta < 90^\circ$. Conversely, the same two molecules at 300 K (bottom panel) are able to rotate and flip when $\cos\theta \sim -1$ and $\theta \sim 180^\circ$. The rotations occurs within 1 – 2 ps indicating a fast dynamics.

We further calculate the angular auto-correlation function (ACF) $\cos\theta_i(t-t_0)$, that is the average over all N atoms and over all possible initial times t_0 during the simulation time Θ , i.e. :

$$A(t) = \langle \hat{n}(t) \cdot \hat{n}(0) \rangle = \frac{1}{N} \sum_i \frac{1}{\Theta - t_0} \sum_{t_1=t+t_0} \hat{n}_i(t_1) \cdot \hat{n}_i(t_0)$$

Figure 6: Molecular autocorrelation function ACF in $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{PbI}_3$ calculated at different temperatures in the range 100-350 K

The ACF is the appropriate tool to evaluate the relaxation dynamics and it is reported in Figure 6 at different temperatures. To this aim we carefully equilibrated a crystal formed by 3024-atoms by means of 0.5 ns long $N\sigma T$ dynamics. The autocorrelation functions were then calculated by saving configurations every 10 fs during 10 ps long runs. Due to the relatively fast molecular dynamics, this time interval is long enough to estimate with the desired accuracy the decay times in the whole range of temperatures of interest (see Figure 6). The long annealing times are critical to get converged results of the correlation functions. Stationarity has been verified by prolongating the runs and by repeating the calculations. We further observe that the results are independent on the initial configurations. We found identical results starting either from cubic crystals with randomly oriented molecules or from orthorhombic lattice with ordered molecules.

At $T > 180$ K the autocorrelation decreases to zero with a faster decay at higher temperature. The decay is exponential as shown by representing data in the log scale (see Figure 7, right panel). At very low temperature the slope is practically zero and the correlation function converges to a constant value $0 < \alpha < 1$.

To further characterize the data it is necessary an analytical function of time $\alpha(t)$ able to

reproduce the atomistic data. Phenomenological functions have been proposed for gas and molten salts. However, such models do not apply to the case of molecular solids for which oscillatory behaviors can be found and a simple analytical form is not available. Here, we make use of an alternative analytical form that is able to include both diffusive and oscillatory behaviors. In particular, the calculated ACF curves (see Figure 7) show features that must be reproduced by the model: (i) an overall exponential decay; (ii) a power law behavior at $t \sim 0$; (iii) a damped oscillation. The exponential decay of the correlation function is a property of diffusive models.¹ As for the power law behavior, we observe that at short times, the correlation corresponds approximately to a free rotation of the molecules and this gives a power law that is independent on the intermolecular forces.¹ Finally, the oscillations and the damping are clearly visible in the atomistic data at low temperature (see Figure 7) and are related to the coupling of the molecules with lattice vibrations. Here we propose a simple analytical function based on the (i,ii,iii) requirements that is able to describe the ACF functions over the whole range of times and temperatures:

$$\alpha(t) = e^{-t/\tau_0} \left[A_1 + \frac{t}{\tau_0} e^{-(t/\tau_1)^n} + (1 - A_1) \cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{\tau_2} t\right) \frac{1}{(t/\tau_3 + 1)^m} \right].$$

$\alpha(t)$ contains four time parameters $\tau_0, \tau_1, \tau_2, \tau_3$.

Figure 7: Analytical modeling (lines) of the molecular auto-correlation functions (symbols)

The parameter τ_0 controls the overall exponential decay $\alpha(t) \sim e^{-t/\tau_0}$; in the limit $\tau_0 \rightarrow \infty$ the curve $\alpha(t)$ is able to model a constant behavior $\alpha(t) \rightarrow A_1 > 0$ as observed at very low temperature; the parameter τ_1 describes the function at $t \sim 0$, where $\alpha(t) \sim (t/\tau_1)^n$ is expected from the diffusive regime. Concerning τ_2 , it corresponds to the period of an harmonic oscillation $\cos(\frac{2\pi}{\tau_2})$ slowly damped by a power law term $\sim (\frac{t}{\tau_3})^{-m}$, this latter controlled by a further time scale τ_3 .

Upon fitting the parameters, the model $\alpha(t)$ nicely reproduces the atomistic ACF data (see Figure 7) in the whole range of times and temperature.

The analysis provides also the temperature dependence of the time constants. In the Arrhenius plot of Figure 8 the result for $\tau_0(T)$, $\tau_1(T)$, $\tau_2(T)$ are reported as filled squares, open circles and empty squares, respectively. The time constants have different temperature dependence and the analysis of the atomistic data suggests the laws:

$$\tau_0(T) \sim e^{\frac{1}{T}} \quad \tau_1(T) \sim \sqrt{\frac{1}{T}} \quad \tau_2(T) \sim 1$$

These different temperature dependences help the physical interpretation of the parameters. The exponential dependence of τ_0 (filled red squares) corresponds to an Arrhenius law where $1/\tau_0 \sim e^{-E_a/kT}$; this can be explained by the existence of an energy barrier E_a needed to tilt the molecules. In the temperature range 180-400 K the atomistic data follow a straight line (red line in Figure 8) corresponding to an activation energy as small as $1.4 \cdot 300k_B \sim 3.5$ kJ/mol. This value is comparable to 2.6 kJ/mol that is the only available experimental data for the thermal activation and it is obtained from infrared absorption measurements³⁹ (corresponding to the open triangles of Figure 8). As already discussed, this barrier is one order of magnitude lower than the one obtained for the static zero temperature collective rotation used to calibrate the model. Below 180 K the molecules tend to remain in their initial orientation and the correlation time τ_0 largely increases, giving rise to an abrupt change of slope of the line fitting the atomistic data (see quasi red vertical line in

Figure 8).

Concerning the parameters, τ_1 , it controls the power law behavior at the early stages of the relaxation process where, within the diffusion theory, the correlation function corresponds to the free motion of the molecule. Considering a classical rigid rotor with moment of inertia I , its energy E is fixed by the angular velocity ω and the rotational period $\frac{2\pi}{\tau}$ through the equation $E = \frac{1}{2}I\omega^2$. Under thermal equilibrium the thermal energy is $E \sim kT$ and the rotational time is expected to be $\tau \sim \omega^{-1} \sim \sqrt{\frac{I}{kT}}$. This is in fact the case for τ_1 (open circles in Figure 8) that follow a square root of $1/T$ (dashed line). The moment of inertia of the molecule for the rotation of the N-C around an axis orthogonal to it and passing through the center of mass can be calculated by the formula $I = \sum_i m_i r_{\perp i}^2$ where $r_{\perp i}$ is the distance of atom i from the axis of rotation. It roughly corresponds to $I = \frac{1}{2}m_{CH_3NH_3}d_{NC}^2$ where $m_{CH_3NH_3} = 32$ a.m.u. is the total mass and 1.5 \AA is the N-C bond length d_{NC} . The reorientation time of the free rotor calculated in this way (using the above moment of inertia of the free molecule) is reported in Figure 8 as shadowed green region and it is shorter (i.e. too fast) with respect to times obtained from IR experiments and atomistic simulations (τ_1). This suggests that τ_1 can be considered the period of free rotation but with an effective inertia moment that is larger than the one of the free molecule. This can be understood in terms of the interaction of the molecule with the embedding crystal.

As for the τ_2 parameter, this time scale does not change with the temperature, with exception of a jump at the orthorhombic phase transition. We conclude that $\frac{1}{\tau_2}$ behaves as an effective normal frequency of the molecule in the potential induced by the embedding lattice; assuming a fixed restoring torque M we have $\tau_2 \sim \sqrt{\frac{M}{I}}$ that is independent on temperature unless the torque M varies (for example due to a different crystallographic structure and environment). Interestingly, the spin-lattice relaxation time of NMR experiments with deuterated molecules provides a subpicosecond time in the same range of τ_2 (see filled triangle).

Figure 8: Temperature dependence of the relaxation times τ_0, τ_1, τ_2 for cation rotation in lead halide perovskites compared to IR and NMR experiments and rigid classical rotators. The width of the rigid rotor curve corresponds to the range of variation of the inertia moment changing the rotation center of the molecule.

In conclusion, we developed a scalable model potential that is able to reproduce the main structural and vibrational properties of the perovskite at room temperature and we have applied the model to the study of the reorientational dynamics of the methylammonium. In agreement with experiments we found that the molecule trajectories exhibit a transition from a dynamics dominated by high symmetry directions at low temperature, to a fast dynamics at room temperature in which the molecule can reorient quasi-randomly. The molecular reorientational correlation function is analyzed by a simple analytical model and the nature of the relaxation times are discussed in terms of their temperature dependence.

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Supporting Information of "Methylammonium Rotational dynamics in Lead Halide Perovskite by Classical Molecular Dynamics: The Role of Temperature"

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Energy as a function of lattice spacing

We report supplemental information about the comparison between DFT and MYP potential during the hydrostatic strain of the MPbI_3 cubic crystal. In Figure 1 the MYP energy-strain relation is compared to DFT-GGA and DFT-LDA calculations. The GGA overestimates the equilibrium lattice spacing ($a_0 = 6.49 \text{ \AA}$) while LDA slightly underestimates ($a = 6.21 \text{ \AA}$). A good agreement is found between MYP ($a_0 = 6.29 \text{ \AA}$) and experiments ($a_0 = 6.32 \text{ \AA}$). In the right panel of Figure 1 the DFT curves are shifted to the MYP equilibrium value.

Figure 1: Left Panel: Energy as a function of lattice spacing of the cubic $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{PbI}_3$ bulk during a hydrostatic deformation for the MYP model potential and for *ab initio* DFT-GGA (black) and DFT-LDA (blue). Right Panel: same curves upon shifting the DFT minima to the MYP value.

Directional maps at the phase transition

In Figure 2 we report additional directional maps calculated at temperatures close to the orthorhombic-to-tetragonal transitions. The maps indicate that during the phase transition the molecules can undergo a collective reorientation switching from the a - b plane into a more vertical orientation along the azimuthal directions -45° and 135° .

Figure 2: Directional maps ($\phi, z = \cos\theta$) as a function of temperature. The maps are obtained by considering the directions of all the 256 molecules of the crystal, sampled every 30 fs during 10 ps of annealing at constant temperature $N\sigma T$

Parameters of the hybrid model (MYP)

We report the parameters of all the interactions of the MYP potential. The parameters are written according to the format of the FIELD file of the DL_POLY code.¹

```

MPbI3
UNITS kcal
MOLECULES 3
Lead
  nummol 256
  atoms 1
  Pb      207.2      2.03
FINISH
Iodine
  nummol 768
  atoms 1
  I      126.90     -1.13
FINISH
ch3nh3
NUMMOL 256
ATOMS      8
H 1.0080 0.54
H 1.0080 0.54
H 1.0080 0.54

```

```

N 14.0100 -1.1
C 12.0100 0.771
H3 1.0080 0.023
H3 1.0080 0.023
H3 1.0080 0.023
bonds          7
harm  5  6  677.4000  1.0910
harm  5  7  677.4000  1.0910
harm  5  8  677.4000  1.0910
harm  4  1  738.0000  1.0330
harm  4  2  738.0000  1.0330
harm  4  3  738.0000  1.0330
harm  4  5  587.2000  1.4990
angles        12
harm  7  5  8  78.0000  110.7400
harm  6  5  7  78.0000  110.7400
harm  6  5  8  78.0000  110.7400
harm  3  4  5  92.4000  110.1100
harm  2  4  3  81.0000  108.1100
harm  2  4  5  92.4000  110.1100
harm  1  4  2  81.0000  108.1100
harm  1  4  3  81.0000  108.1100
harm  1  4  5  92.4000  110.1100
harm  4  5  6  98.0000  107.9100
harm  4  5  7  98.0000  107.9100
harm  4  5  8  98.0000  107.9100
dihedrals     9
cos  3  4  5  6  0.1556  0.0000  3.0000  0.833  0.500
cos  3  4  5  7  0.1556  0.0000  3.0000  0.833  0.500
cos  3  4  5  8  0.1556  0.0000  3.0000  0.833  0.500
cos  2  4  5  6  0.1556  0.0000  3.0000  0.833  0.500
cos  2  4  5  7  0.1556  0.0000  3.0000  0.833  0.500
cos  2  4  5  8  0.1556  0.0000  3.0000  0.833  0.500
cos  1  4  5  6  0.1556  0.0000  3.0000  0.833  0.500
cos  1  4  5  7  0.1556  0.0000  3.0000  0.833  0.500
cos  1  4  5  8  0.1556  0.0000  3.0000  0.833  0.500
FINISH
vdw 21
Pb Pb buck    70359906.629702  0.131258  0.000000
Pb I  buck    103496.133010  0.321737  0.000000
I  I  buck    22793.338582  0.482217  696.949542
Pb N  buck    32690390.937995  0.150947  0.000000
Pb H  lj       0.0140  2.26454
Pb C  buck    32690390.937995  0.150947  0.000000
Pb H3 lj       0.0140  2.70999
I  N  buck    112936.714213  0.342426  0.000000
I  H  lj       0.0574  2.75000
I  C  buck    112936.714213  0.342426  0.000000
I  H3 lj       0.0574  3.10000
N  N  lj       0.1700  3.25000
N  H  lj       0.0517  2.15950
N  C  lj       0.1364  3.32480
N  H3 lj       0.0517  2.60500
H  H  lj       0.0157  1.06910

```

H	C	lj	0.0414	2.23440
H	H3	lj	0.0157	1.51450
C	C	lj	0.1094	3.39970
C	H3	lj	0.0414	2.67980
H3	H3	lj	0.0157	1.96000
CLOSE				

Parameters have been reported with all the digits used in the calculations. The most critical parameters are those related to distances (the second coefficients of buck and lj interactions). A variation of the N-I distance from 0.340 to 0.342 is able to decrease the transition temperature in the dynamics of the molecules by tens of Kelvin degrees. The sensitivity of the model to the N-I interaction is consistent with the low energy barrier for molecular rotations and I-Pb-I distortions. The use of all the digits for these kinds of interactions is recommended. The coefficients of the Buckingham terms depend on the chemical species (Pb,I,C,N) and vary by four orders of magnitude. It is recommended to use at least 10 digits.

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